

Assessing the spatial accuracy of geocoding flood-related imagery using Vision Language Models

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Abstract

While the capabilities of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Visual Language Models (VLMs) for various classification tasks have advanced significantly, their potential for location inference remains largely underexplored. Therefore, this study evaluates the performance of four prominent models — BLIP-2, LLaVA1.6, OpenFlamingo, and GPT-4o — for geocoding flood-related images from Flickr. Model inferences are compared against the original photo locations and human-labelled assessments. Our findings reveal that GPT-4o achieves the highest spatial accuracy (median deviation of 89.12 km). OpenFlamingo geocodes the highest number of images (90.7%), albeit with fluctuating quality (median 408.35 km), while still outperforming the human annotators. LLaVA1.6 geocodes only 18.9% of all images, while BLIP-2 exhibits the highest median deviation (1,781 km). We observe a spatial bias in our results, with inferences being most accurate in Central Europe. Additionally, model results improve when images feature recognisable landmarks. The proposed workflow could significantly increase the amount of geocoded web-based data available for disaster management, though further research is required to enhance accuracy across diverse geographic contexts.

Keywords: location inference, disaster management, Vision Language Models, geocoding, Flickr

1 Introduction

Generative [Large Language Models \(LLMs\)](#) have recently seen a significant increase in their use, particularly since the launch of OpenAI’s ChatGPT in November 2022. This includes tasks such as creating customised texts, performing various classification tasks, and answering specific questions

[1]. While the inputs that can be fed to the models were initially limited to textual content, the processing of multimodal and visual data by generative LLMs has become increasingly popular, with simultaneous improvements in the quality of their outputs [2].

Models that are capable of understanding, processing, and generating both textual and visual content are referred to as Vision Language Models (VLMs). So far, many studies have focused on the semantic correctness of the model outputs of strictly textual models and VLMs (e.g. Johnson et al. [3]). Although many of the model inputs and outputs might contain implicit or even explicit spatial information (e.g. mentioned toponyms, spatial reasoning) [4, 5], little attention has been paid to the accuracy of VLMs results in relation to geolocations.

Outside of generating imagery based on the demands of a user, VLMs are often used to derive information about the content of pictures. For instance, a prompt can be written to check an image for the existence of a specific feature or to derive a caption that summarises the image content [6]. In some cases, such captions may include a geolocation. However, these geolocations can also be so-called hallucinations of the model, i.e. a freely invented information that is not related to real-world circumstances. The frequency and probability of such incorrect geolocations in VLM outputs have not yet been sufficiently researched [7].

While unsolicited geoinformation might be featured in the outputs of generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) models, VLMs can also be explicitly asked to provide spatial information, e.g. coordinates or location names, from input imagery. This challenging task is referred to as visual place recognition [8]. In this study, we investigated how accurate these spatial inferences are, using four state-of-the-art VLMs: BLIP-2, LLaVA1.6, OpenFlamingo, and GPT-4o.

Web content plays a crucial role in disaster management by providing near-real time information about on-the-ground conditions. Social media platforms, in particular, are valuable sources of disaster-related texts and images [9, 10]. However, most of the data lacks a georeference [11] or contains only very coarse geometries, e.g. in the form of a place mention or a bounding box [12]. Consequently, the development of advanced geocoding methods has become increasingly important to improve the spatial accuracy of such data. The aim of our study is therefore to improve the geocoding of imagery for disaster management purposes, i.e. to enable more precise localisation of potentially affected areas or populations. In this context, we deliberately focus on VLMs, as their dual ability to process text and images makes them particularly suitable for analysing social media data.

The use of AI and Machine Learning (ML) in a disaster management context has been explored by many studies. Since earth observation data remains the central data source in the evaluation of most disasters triggered by environmental hazards, much research on AI-based image classification methods exists (e.g. Li et al. [13]). Additionally, many ML-based methodologies have been proposed in the area of social media analysis to derive relevant information from texts or imagery (e.g. Hanny and Resch [14], de Bruijn et al. [15]). However, this current generation of VLMs has not yet been sufficiently evaluated for use for disaster management purposes. While they show significant potential, especially for social media analyses, it remains unclear how useful their outputs actually are, in particular with regard to their spatial accuracy. Furthermore, it remains unexamined whether or to what extent the model results are subject to spatial bias, i.e. whether performance is better in certain regions. Our study provides first insights into the quality of explicit geoinformation derived from disaster-related imagery by VLMs.

To achieve this, we utilised georeferenced images from Flickr, a social media platform for the sharing of pictures and videos. For comparability purposes, we focused on imagery on the same topic, i.e. imagery containing flooded areas. We fed all of these pictures to several VLMs with the task of inferring a location from each picture. We used this information to compare these coordinates with the coordinates of the individual images provided by Flickr. In an additional step, we asked human annotators to perform the same tasks as the VLMs on a subset of the images to assess the difficulty of the classification task. Consequently, we aimed to answer the following research questions:

RQ1: How accurately can state-of-the-art Vision Language Models geocode flood-related imagery?

RQ2: Do the VLMs exhibit any spatial bias in geocoding flood-related imagery?

2 Literature review

Web data, especially from social media platforms, has already proven to be highly useful for disaster management. For this purpose, methodologies for topic modelling [16], disaster-relatedness classification [17, 18], and relevance classification [19] have been proposed in the literature. However, not only text from social media can provide insightful information about disasters, but also attached image content. Here, the primary goal is to automatically categorise the content of posted images or videos. For example, [Convolutional Neural Network \(CNN\)](#)-based methodologies to identify images of floods posted on Twitter were developed by Barz et al. [20] and Madichetty and Muthukumarasamy [21]. Hassan et al. [22] propose a method combining a [CNN](#) with transfer learning to perform sentiment analysis on disaster-related imagery. Li and Xie [23] analyse which kind of image characteristics lead to higher user engagement on social media, using the Google Cloud Vision [Application Programming Interface \(API\)](#) to classify the image content. Asif et al. [24] propose a taxonomy-based classification with YOLOv4 for disaster-related imagery, while Hariharan et al. [25] classify water levels and estimate the number of people on flood-related imagery and integrate these with Tweet texts and geolocations. Pally and Samadi [26] develop a [CNN](#)-based pipeline for the classification of flood-related imagery with the aim of utilising it for live monitoring of rivers. This includes the delineation of water surfaces and the estimation of water levels. While the models in these studies also fall under deep learning methods, they do not use [VLMs](#).

Some of the most important state-of-the-art [VLMs](#) include fusion encoders (e.g. VisualBERT, VisualGPT) and dual encoders (e.g. [Contrastive Language-Image Pre-Training \(CLIP\)](#), [Bootstrapping Language-Image Pre-training for Unified Vision-Language Understanding and Generation \(BLIP\)](#), Flamingo) [27]. They were all pre-trained based on a large-scale dataset and then fine-tuned for more specific tasks, which has become the most prevalent paradigm in deep learning [2]. Since the [VLMs](#) used in this analysis are relatively new [28], there are not yet many studies utilising them. Focusing on the model training, Chen et al. [29] present MiniGPT-v2 which outperforms other models such as BLIP-2 in [Visual Question Answering \(VQA\)](#) tasks, while Bai et al. [30] introduce Qwen-VL, which is trained on an English and Chinese dataset and thus enables multilingual conversations. In the media-effective, on-going discourse about ChatGPT, BLIP-2 has already been proposed as a tool for automatic question answering for visual content [31]. Liu et al. [32] compare the performance of BLIP-2 against other similar models such as OpenFlamingo, LLaVa or MiniGPT4. Chen et al. [33] find that BLIP-2 outperforms Flamingo and BLIP considerably for video captioning. Juhász et al. [34] propose a workflow to tag road segments from [OpenStreetMap \(OSM\)](#) that employs BLIP-2, even though they still achieve a quite low accuracy. Focusing on the quality of the model outputs, Chauhan et al. [35] find significant, though not overly frequent, racial and gender biases in OpenFlamingo imagery, such as a disproportionate representation of Caucasians and men in jobs like doctors or police officers. Similarly, Burda-Lassen et al. [36] investigate the cultural awareness of [VLMs](#) in analysing imagery of dances and other tangible and intangible cultural heritage, finding a quite low awareness for OpenFlamingo. Liu et al. [7] discuss potential sources for hallucinations, i.e. invented features, in semantic extractions from [VLMs](#), such as low image resolution or the excessive incorporation of randomness. Addressing a more spatial topic, Wang et al. [5] report an underperformance of [VLMs](#) in spatial reasoning in comparison to strictly textual [LLMs](#), conducting their tests e.g. on a maze. There are also [VLMs](#) specialised in the domain of remote sensing imagery [27], such as the GeoChat for [VQA](#) [37].

While there is plenty of literature about extracting locations from text and subsequently geocoding them [38], image content has so far rarely been used for this kind of task. Nevertheless, there are some relevant studies about inferring locations from imagery. Gallagher et al. [39] also use Flickr images to determine image locations, basing their approach on user tags and user location probability maps. However, their approach predates the widespread use of [VLMs](#). Laumer et al. [40] detect trees in Google Street View imagery using a Faster R-CNN model and manage to assign 38% of them to a geolocation. However, they run their analysis only on data from California, i.e. try to geocode quite precise locations. Sathianarayanan et al. [41] develop a method to extract phone numbers from Google Street View imagery in Taiwan and geocode them via Google Maps, achieving precision in the metre range. Haas et al. [8] present a zero-shot approach using on a pre-trained [CLIP](#) model and synthetic captions to infer geolocations from Google Street View imagery. Basing their work on street-level imagery from GeoGuesser, Haas et al. [42] train a location inference model which can locate 40% of its imagery within a 25 km radius of the original location. They additionally present a more general model trained on Flickr imagery, which achieves slightly lower accuracies. Wazzan et al. [43] evaluates

the performance of LLM-based search engines for the determination of an image geolocation, finding that tradition search engines still outperform them.

Data from the image and video platform Flickr, which is the basis for our study, has been utilised in various publications with diverse thematic backgrounds. Lee et al. [44] use automatic, deep-learning-based tagging of Flickr imagery to analyse cultural ecosystem services in Eastern Germany. Zheng et al. [45] propose a home location detection based on geotagged Flickr images and mobility patterns. Yan et al. [46] compare automatically generated tags from Flickr with land cover and land use information in California. Islam and Zhang [47] use imagery from Flickr to perform visual sentiment analysis, finding that the identification of positive pictures works better with their approach. In the context of disaster management, Panteras et al. [48] propose a method to derive potential locations of disaster-related Flickr images from frequently occurring toponyms on Twitter. There are several other studies using Flickr imagery, including on the perception of street art [49], the reaction to Brexit [50], tourist flow predictions [51], and the common features of touristic photographs [52].

3 Methodology

In the following, we describe our methodological approach. Figure 1 shows a schematic overview of our methods.

Figure 1: Overview of the study workflow.

3.1 Data acquisition

To collect flood-related imagery, we accessed data from the Flickr API. For this, we only queried images with "geo" coordinates. It was assumed that these coordinates corresponded to the GPS coordinates of the camera or phone that produced the picture. Additionally, we used the keyword "flood" in eleven languages for our queries (cf. Table 1). In total, we collected and downloaded 1,580 images with a point location. Duplicates (i.e. pictures showing the same scenery) and unsuitable images (e.g. images not showing flooded areas or images inside buildings) were then manually removed. After filtering, a total of 353 georeferenced, flood-related pictures remained. As shown in Figure 1 in the appendix, the dataset exhibited a clear bias towards Central Europe, while other world regions were underrepresented.

Language	Keyword	Language	Keyword
English	<i>flood</i>	French	<i>inondation</i>
	<i>inundation</i>	Dutch	<i>overstroming</i>
German	<i>überschwemmung</i>	Swedish	<i>översvämning</i>
	<i>hochwasser</i>	Danish	<i>oversvømmelse</i>
Spanish	<i>inundación</i>	Russian	<i>наводнение</i>
Portuguese	<i>inundação</i>	Greek	<i>πλημμύρα</i>
Italian	<i>inondazione</i>		

Table 1: List of keywords used for Flickr API queries.

3.2 Vision Language Models

To derive information from the images, we employed several **VLMs** that are capable of answering explicit questions from a person to an image, so-called **VQA**. All of the models were trained on large image-text datasets, leveraging a visual transformer architecture to convert visual features, extracted by a pre-trained and frozen visual encoder, into tokens. Each image was processed by the following pre-trained **VLMs** without additional model fine-tuning:

- *blip2-flan-t5-xxl* (short: BLIP-2) utilises a frozen ViT-L/14 visual encoder from CLIP [53], paired with the Flan-T5-XXL LLM [54]. The training process was conducted on 129 million image-text pairs drawn from diverse datasets including COCO, CC12M, CC3M, SBU, and Visual Genome, supplemented by an additional 115 million images from the LAION400M dataset [28]. The location inference prompt for BLIP-2 was "In what city is this image located?".
- *llava-v1.6-vicuna-13b* (short: LLaVA1.6) employs a frozen ViT-L/14 visual encoder from CLIP in conjunction with the Vicuna-13B-v1.5 LLM [55]. The model was trained on more than 500,000 image-text pairs from LAION, CC, and SBU, with captions by BLIP [56]. Additionally, the training incorporated 158,000 GPT-generated multimodal instruction-following examples, 500,000 academic-task-oriented VQA data points, 50,000 instances from a GPT-4V data mixture, and 40,000 ShareGPT data examples [57]. The location inference prompt for LLaVA1.6 was "In what city is this image located?".
- *OpenFlamingo-3B-vitl-mpt1b* (short: OpenFlamingo) integrates a frozen ViT-L/14 visual encoder from CLIP with the MPT-1B LLM. The model was trained using datasets from LAION-2B and Multimodal C4 [58]. The location inference prompt for OpenFlamingo was "<image>An image of the city of...".
- *GPT-4o* features a multimodal architecture combining a ViT-based visual encoder with an advanced language model. It was trained on billions of image-text pairs from datasets like COCO, Visual Genome, OpenImages, and LAION [59]. The location inference prompt for GPT-4o was "In what city is this image located? Only return the city name".

The first three models were hosted on a high-performance computing environment operating on Red Hat 8.5, powered by an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6148 CPU @ 2.40GHz, and equipped with two Tesla V100 PCIe 32GB GPUs utilising CUDA 12.0. This setup provided the necessary computational resources to efficiently handle the extensive data processing tasks. Only GPT-4o was used via the OpenAI API.

Since the results of the models were often texts with additional, but unneeded information, we applied some post-processing (e.g. converting the original output "This image is located in Venice, Italy." to "Venice, Italy"). Following Serere et al. [38], we performed location extraction on the remaining texts using SpaCy and geocoded these locations using the Nominatim API, a geocoder based on OSM. If a suitable location was identified in the Nominatim database, a pair of coordinates was returned, i.e. the inferred geolocation of the respective image. This was done for the output of all the **VLMs** and each image.

To evaluate the accuracy of these georeferences, we used two different metrics: First, the distance in metres between the geocoded result of the **VLM** and the original image coordinates was calculated. Secondly, we determined whether the **VLM** results and the original location were within the same country and continent. For this purpose, we accessed global data on country-level administrative boundaries from World Food Programme [60].

4 Results

In the following, we present the results of our VLM-based image location detection and compare them to the actual geolocation of the Flickr images. Furthermore, we also describe the results of the labelling conducted by our human annotators.

4.1 Geocoded VLM results

For each model, Table 2 shows the minimum, maximum, mean, and median distances, as well as the standard deviation, between the geocoded and the original location of the image. Additionally, the number of successfully geocoded images is provided. We observed that the LLaVA1.6 model was only able to provide geocodeable locations for 18.9% of all images, whereas the OpenFlamingo model identified locations for 90.7% of all images. Similarly, GPT-4o was able to provide geocodeable locations for 70.5% of all images. The results of BLIP-2 had the highest mean and median distances, i.e. the most incorrect inferences. OpenFlamingo and LLaVA1.6 performed similarly, while GPT-4o scored the lowest mean and median distances. GPT-4o successfully geocoded 64 images within 5 km and 35 images within 1 km of their original location, while OpenFlamingo only provided georeferences for 13 images within 5 km and 10 images within 1 km.

model	#geocoded	ratio [%]	distances [km]				
			min	max	mean	median	std dev
BLIP-2	187	53.0	1.05	19,286.94	3,795.87	1,781.33	3,896.36
LLaVA1.6	67	18.9	0.26	10,014.64	1,006.69	335.74	2,091.76
OpenFlamingo	320	90.7	0.14	19,221.06	1,575.39	408.35	3,155.91
GPT-4o	249	70.5	0.11	18,614.69	929.63	89.12	2,613.99
human annotators	49	-	0.11	18,188.19	2,855.42	1,071.12	4,156.76

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of geocoding results for LLMs and human annotators (min = minimum, max = maximum, std dev = standard deviation).

Figure 2 shows a comparison of the performances for the VLMs we used. It displays that GPT-4o (mean: 929.63 km) inferred locations considerably closer to the original georeference of the image than OpenFlamingo (1,575.39 km), LLaVA1.6 (1,006.69 km), and BLIP-2 (3,795.87 km). Additionally, Figure 3 shows a scatterplot comparison between the results of OpenFlamingo and BLIP-2. It becomes apparent that many of the model results were relatively similar, clustering below the 2,500 km distance threshold. However, there were also several images where the results deviated heavily. Figure 4 compares the results of OpenFlamingo and GPT-4o, showing a strong cluster below the 500 km distance threshold. While GPT-4o generally outperformed OpenFlamingo, there were still some occasion where OpenFlamingo inferred more accurate georeferences.

To analyse whether the VLMs exhibited spatial bias with regard to the quality of their results, we investigated the spatial distribution of the geocoded locations. Visualisations for the results of BLIP-2 and LLaVA1.6 are provided in the appendix, in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively. Figure 5 shows the distribution together with the quality of the model results for OpenFlamingo. Most of the images with a difference of less than 100 kilometres between the position determined by the VLM and the actual location were located in Central Europe. The UK, Germany, Netherlands and France were particularly worth mentioning. Other notable locations were found on the US East Coast, in Egypt and in India. In Latin America, Asia and Australia, no images were geocoded with a spatial accuracy of less than 100 kilometres. Figure 6 shows the distribution of results for GPT-4o. Most of the predicted image locations with a spatial accuracy smaller than 50 km were once again located in central Europe. However, there were also several pictures with good predictions in the USA, South East Asia and even some in Brazil and Northern Africa. It should be noted that some points, with different geocoding quality, are overlapping on the maps.

Moreover, we compared the quality of the geocoding results to global population distribution. For this, we calculated the correlation between the distance between geocoded location and original location

Figure 2: Comparison of VLM distances. Distances were logarithmised.

Figure 3: Comparison of distances between OpenFlamingo and BLIP-2 on picture-level.

and the population density (Global Human Settlement Layer [61], spatial resolution: 1 km). For all models, we found slightly negative, but not statistically significant correlations (OpenFlamingo: -0.087 (p-value: 0.120), BLIP-2: -0.077 (p-value: 0.296), LLaVA1.6: -0.201 (p-value: 0.103), GPT-4o: -0.105 (p-value: 0.098)).

To assess the spatial distribution of our data, we calculated the Global Moran's I statistic (cf. Formula 1) and the Local Moran's I statistic (cf. Formula 2):

$$I = \frac{N}{W} \cdot \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} (x_i - \bar{x})(x_j - \bar{x})}{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (1)$$

Figure 4: Comparison of distances between OpenFlamingo and GPT-4o on picture-level. Outliers above 2,500 km were excluded for better readability.

$$I_i = \frac{(x_i - \bar{x})}{m_2} \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij}(x_j - \bar{x}) \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of observations, W is the sum of all the weights, x_i and x_j are values of the variable at locations i and j , respectively, \bar{x} is the mean of the values, w_{ij} is the spatial weight between locations i and j , and m_2 is the variance of x [62].

For this analysis, we defined a distance-based spatial neighbourhood with several thresholds (cf. Table 3). For all models and distance thresholds, the Moran’s I was positive and mostly statistically significant, ranging between 0.05 and 0.52. Depending on the distance band, this was at least an indication of weak spatial autocorrelation, i.e. a slight clustering of similar values. We calculated the Local Moran’s I statistic for OpenFlamingo and GPT-4o (cf. Figure 7) on their respective European subsets, where most Flickr images originated. Figure 5 in the appendix shows that there was a low-low cluster for the OpenFlamingo results in France, as well as in parts of Germany, the UK, and Northern Italy. On the other hand, high values seemed to cluster in Eastern Europe and in the South of France. However, many of the observations (65.7%) were statistically insignificant. For the GPT-4o results, this was even the case for 78.0% of all data points. Consequently, the distribution of low-low clusters also differed a bit, which clusters in Central France and South Western Germany. Similarly to the OpenFlamingo results, there were very few high-high clusters, i.e. areas where very wrong location inferences clustered. Since the choice of spatial weights matrix generally strongly influences the output of spatial autocorrelation-based analyses, we also computed the Local Moran’s based on a *k*-nearest neighbour (KNN) ($n=16$) approach, with relatively similar results regarding the location of low-low clusters (Central France, Northern Italy, Alps).

Figure 5: Quality of OpenFlamingo geocoding results. Each points corresponds to the original location from Flickr. The colours signify the quality of the VLM geocoding. The basemap in all figures is "Carto Light Grey".

Model	BLIP-2	OpenFlamingo	LLaVA1.6	GPT-4o
Threshold [km]				
100	0.51281 (0.001)	0.32695 (0.002)	0.51384 (0.123)	0.34486 (0.018)
500	0.19031 (0.000)	0.10463 (0.003)	0.25909 (0.069)	0.12137 (0.012)
1000	0.05698 (0.008)	0.05723 (0.000)	0.16966 (0.001)	0.05064 (0.007)

Table 3: Global Moran’s I, based on different distance thresholds for spatial weights matrix. P-values are included in brackets.

4.2 Comparison with human annotators

As part of our evaluation strategy, we had eight human annotators perform the same task as the VLMs. For this, we set up a Streamlit app that showed the user each image and an interactive OSM map. The task was then to assign a location for each image by clicking on the map. As with the VLMs, the human annotator received no additional information beyond the picture itself. All of the participants in the study were employees of the Department of Geoinformatics at the University of Salzburg and could hence be regarded as experts in the geospatial domain. Each annotator was provided with 49 images with original locations distributed worldwide.

We aggregated the results of these human annotators by calculating the mean and median distance between the original photo coordinates and the location assigned by the respective user. Descriptive statistics can be found in Table 2. At 2,855 km, the average distance for the human annotators was significantly higher than for the GPT-4o, OpenFlamingo, and LLaVA1.6 models, but lower than for BLIP-2. The same was observed for the median distance. However, the smallest distance between the estimated and real location was achieved by a human (0.11 km), although being practically identical to GPT-4o best inference. The overall worst guess of human annotators was still better (18,188 km) than for GPT-4o (18,614 km), OpenFlamingo (19,221 km), and BLIP-2 (19,286 km), but significantly worse than for LLaVA1.6 (10,014 km).

Distance to original location
 • <10km • 10-50km • 50-100km • 100-500km • >500km

Figure 6: Quality of GPT-4o geocoding results. Each points corresponds to the original location from Flickr. The colours signify the quality of the VLM geocoding.

Local Moran's I cluster
 • high-high • high-low • low-high • low-low • insignificant

Figure 7: Local Moran's I for GPT-4o based on inverse distance spatial weights matrix.

Table 4 shows how often the human annotators identified a location in the same country and continent as the original Flickr image. The correct country was identified in only 34.0% of cases, while 78.1% of the images were georeferenced on the correct continent. GPT-4o performed best, identifying the correct country for 78.7% and correct continent for 93.0% of the images. BLIP-2 showed nearly identical performance to the human annotators at country level, albeit on the entire dataset and not on the sample, but performed worse when matching with the continents. OpenFlamingo was able to find the correct country for more than half of the images (53.1%). LLaVA1.6 performed even better with 60.7% correct countries, but was only able to geocode a fraction of the images. Additionally, Table 5

		country	continent
human annotators	True	104 (34.0%)	239 (78.1%)
	False	202 (66.0%)	67 (21.9%)
OpenFlamingo	True	170 (53.1%)	282 (88.1%)
	False	150 (46.9%)	38 (11.9%)
LLaVA1.6	True	34 (60.7%)	54 (96.4%)
	False	22 (39.3%)	2 (3.6%)
BLIP-2	True	89 (34.1%)	174 (66.7%)
	False	172 (65.9%)	87 (33.3%)
GPT-4o	True	181 (78.7%)	214 (93.0%)
	False	49 (7.0%)	16 (21.3%)

Table 4: Error matrix for country and continent matching of locations.

Rank	1	2	3	4	5
human annotators	France	Germany	UK	USA	Mexico
Open Flamingo	France	Germany	USA	UK	Russia
LLaVA1.6	France	Germany	USA	UK	Vietnam
BLIP-2	USA	UK	Russia	Germany	France
GPT-4o	France	Germany	USA	UK	Spain
Flickr images	France	Germany	USA	Russia	UK

Table 5: Most frequent countries. For the human annotators and [VLM](#) output this refers to the most frequently correctly identified countries. For the Flickr images, it refers to the original locations.

shows the most frequently correctly identified countries for all models and the human annotators. The selection of countries and order was quite similar for all, with France, Germany and the USA appearing most often. BLIP-2, the model with the highest average deviation, was the only [VLM](#) where the Central European countries were not identified most frequently. However, it should also be noted that these were the countries with the most data in our Flickr dataset.

Finally, we compared the distance between the [VLM](#)-derived coordinates and those assigned by human annotators for each image. Figure 8 shows the distribution of our average human annotator results in relation to the distances derived by GPT-4o, the best performing [VLM](#). For both, most distances clustered below 2,000 km, which still represented a very large offset. However, the human annotators had considerably more outliers. Given the large scatter in both human annotator and model distances, this representation could therefore be potentially misleading. Figure 4 in the appendix therefore shows the same distribution with logarithmised axes.

Figure 8: Comparison of distances between GPT-4o and human annotator results. The marginal plots show histograms for the distribution of the respective variable.

5 Discussion

We begin by discussing the results of our study, with a focus on the quality of the [VLM](#) outputs. Next, we address the limitations of our analysis and outline potential directions for future research.

5.1 Discussion of results

Our study revealed differences in the image location inference performance of the [VLMs](#). For once, the amount of geocodeable images varied heavily between the models. Notably, the LLaVA1.6 model yielded a very low number of usable results. To evaluate the [VLM](#) performance in more detail, we manually reviewed the outliers in our results. Examples of these pictures are shown in [Figure 9](#). For OpenFlamingo, the largest deviations between the predicted and actual location were mainly observed for images exclusively featuring landscapes. The pictures contained almost only vegetation and water surfaces, with very few man-made elements present, such as bridges, street lamps or road signs. Consequently, there were few clear indications to unambiguously identify the locations. Only one image, originally from Mercedes, Uruguay, contained architectural hints ([Figure 9d](#)), while an image from Buenos Aires, Argentina featured Spanish texts. Another picture included a street sign pointing to the Elbe River in Germany, which the model failed to notice or comprehend. Notably, many of these wrongly classified pictures had their original locations in Latin America. For the best results, it was quite noticeable that these mostly included rather famous landmarks. Among those were the Chapel Bridge in Lucerne, Switzerland; Piazza San Marco in Venice, Italy ([Figure 9c](#)); the Dresden Skyline, Germany; the Philae temple complex in Egypt; the Speicherstadt district in Hamburg, Germany, the Sanctuary of Our Lady of Lourdes, France; and the Pont de Grenelle in Paris, France ([Figure 9e](#)). One image from Jakarta, Indonesia featured an uncensored license plate ([Figure 9a](#), edited), which might have been identified by the model. For GPT-4o, some of the best performances were achieved for images showing the German town of Miltenberg; the Chapel Bridge in Lucerne, Switzerland; the Pont Saint-Laurent in Mâcon, France; the town of Bradford-on-Avon, UK; and the old town of Paraty, Brazil. Interestingly, the most incorrect inference also featured a bridge in Western Brazil, which was geocoded to Southern Thailand. The model also struggled with some imagery containing only landscapes, e.g. geocoding an image from New South Wales, Australia to Ipswich, UK. On the other

hand, it correctly identified an image, that only featured inundated vegetation, as originating from Northern Germany. It also demonstrated a generally strong understanding of local architecture, e.g. correctly identifying the city of Koblenz, Germany on a picture featuring only ordinary houses. For a picture showing a street sign pointing to Wertheim, Germany, it seemingly only extracted the text. The pictures that it could not geocode mainly only featured landscapes with very few indications of their original location.

Figure 9: Exemplary Flickr images used in analysis. All photos were edited to a 16:9 ratio. (a) Jakarta, Indonesia, (b) Biel, Switzerland, (c) Piazza San Marco, Venice, Italy, (d) Mercedes, Uruguay, (e) Pont de Grenelle, Paris, France, (f) Cognac, France.

As shown in Figure 3, the performance of OpenFlamingo and BLIP-2 was similar for many pictures. We manually reviewed the images with the largest deviations between the models. In most cases, these pictures did not feature any clear landmarks (e.g. Figure 9b). However, many of the images included man-made landscape features (e.g. houses, boats, bridges, quay walls; cf. Figure 9f). While most of these images with high deviations originated from Europe, there were also some images from South America and Asia. On the other hand, the pictures with the highest correspondence - often even the same textual output geolocation - were more likely to include landmarks (e.g. London skyline; the town of Miltenberg, Germany or the port of Hamburg, Germany). All but one of the 25 pictures with the smallest deviation were located in Europe.

In our analysis, we observed several indications of spatial bias in the models. Most relatively accurate results (< 100 km distance) were located in Central Europe or the USA and therefore in regions likely overrepresented in training data. For rather underrepresented world regions such as Africa, Latin America or parts of Asia, the performance of the VLMs was, as expected, considerably worse. This

was also reflected in the Local Moran’s I values that indicated low-low clusters in Central Europe, i.e. a clustering of images that the respective VLM was able to geocode rather well. Although the exact spatial distribution of the training datasets for the VLMs used here is not publicly available, the high amount of English-language captions in the LAION-5B dataset (39.6%) suggests that this spatial bias is due to an existing focus on images from English-speaking and thus predominantly Western regions [63]. Further, we hypothesised that the model’s performances might be related to population density, i.e. inferring more accurate locations in urban areas. Although our analysis revealed slight correlations that suggest this relationship, these correlations were statistically insignificant. As a result, these findings should be interpreted as preliminary and not conclusive. This could also be related to our rather small sample size, influenced by the data source, and the specificity of the topic.

5.2 Discussion of methodology

We chose to compare the performance of four VLMs that were considered state-of-the-art at the time of our study. Given the rapidly evolving landscape of AI, new models with similar or improved capabilities to those featured in this paper are being released with a high frequency. This, in turn, opens up many opportunities for future studies. Other large VQA models, such as Phi-3 Vision-128K-In and LLaVA-Next, have potential to improve semantic classification and, thus, also to enable more fine-grained geocoding. These emerging models feature more sophisticated architectures and leverage larger, more diverse training datasets. Whether this will lead to enhanced accuracy, remains to be tested. However, it is important to note that the results of our study could likely be improved by some more model-specific prompt engineering. In this context, advanced prompting approaches (e.g. chain-of-thought prompting) could also be explored. The impact of such techniques on the spatial accuracy of the results should be investigated in future studies.

While we were investigating spatial bias in our classification results, it is important to acknowledge the clear selection bias in our Flickr dataset. As we selected the images based on keywords, our dataset was heavily skewed towards images from Europe. Some regions (e.g. Africa) were underrepresented in our data sample, likely due to the Flickr user base’s geographic distribution. Furthermore, there was a certain spatial bias among the human annotators, as the majority of the participants were from Central Europe and therefore most familiar with this region of the world. It is therefore not surprising that images from France and Germany were the most likely to be georeferenced rather accurately.

We chose Flickr as our data source, assuming that it would provide more accurate geotags than other social media platforms with visual content, since at least some of the images still contain metadata recorded by the camera device at the time the picture was taken [64]. However, manually verifying for each picture that this position had not been altered afterwards by the user was not feasible. In a study on images of churches, Hauff [65] finds that the quality of a geotag on Flickr depends heavily on the popularity of a place. In 58.8% of their data, the geotag was within 1 km of the actual location. Although this may have introduced some inaccuracy, it should not have impacted the validity of our results greatly, since most of our inferences were further than 100 km from the actual image location.

We also need to acknowledge the general difficulty in geocoding the provided imagery. For some pictures, clear indications made it easier for a person (or model) to recognise their location. These included street signs explicitly referring to the location, or billboards providing (at least) information about the local language. In a few cases, specific landmarks were also recognisable, such as the Eiffel Tower. However, most images featured solely a flooded landscape, where the geomorphological features, vegetation, or the architectural style of existing buildings were the only clues to the location. As a result, many of these images were difficult to geocode, even for humans with strong geographic knowledge. This was emphasised by the fact that the positions assigned by the annotators for most of the pictures were extremely different, sometimes even being placed on different continents.

We chose to analyse highly domain-specific data in this paper to minimise additional factors influencing the model performances. However, the question remains whether model performance for flood-related imagery is better or worse than for other topics, e.g. regular landscape pictures or pictures of other types of disasters. We assume that the models would perform better for images without disasters, as such pictures are more common in the training data. Additionally, such images usually contain fewer confounding image components or visual obstructions. Furthermore, it should be analysed whether and to what extent other image characteristics, such as angle, exposure ratios, and resolution, influence the analysis capabilities of the models.

Many ethical concerns regarding recent advances in AI have been raised. This is also true for the work presented here. While our goal was to infer locations of disaster-related imagery to support the disaster response process in the long run, this methodology could easily be misused to infer the location of specific individuals, e.g. from livestream videos. However, our results showed that the currently existing models do not yet have the capability to generate such spatially accurate information. Given the rapid developments in the field of AI, it is likely that such capabilities will be possible in the future [42].

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we evaluated the performance of state-of-the-art VLMs in inferring geolocations from flood-related Flickr imagery. For this, we compared the model outputs (OpenFlamingo, LLaVA1.6, BLIP-2, GPT-4o) to the original georeference of the respective image and locations inferred by human annotators. While OpenFlamingo was able to geocode the largest number of images, the results from GPT-4o generally had the highest spatial accuracy. LLaVA1.6 geocoded the smallest number of images, although with the second best performance on average, whereas BLIP-2 consistently produced the weakest results of all models. Notably, the first three models outperformed the human annotators, highlighting the inherent difficulty of geocoding ambiguous imagery. Accordingly, our results showed considerable variation in spatial accuracy of inferred image locations across all VLMs.

Our findings suggest that current VLMs possess a certain capacity to infer locations from flood-related imagery, particularly when the images contain recognisable spatial features, such as architectural landmarks (RQ1). However, with respect to RQ2, we identified some spatial bias in the model performances, focusing on the OpenFlamingo and GPT-4o models. Using Local Moran’s I analysis and other methods, we found that locations inferred from imagery in Central Europe and parts of the USA exhibited higher spatial accuracy than those from other world regions. Particularly in Latin America, we encountered poor location inference results. Hence, more research is needed to improve geocoding accuracy of VLMs in diverse geographic contexts, particularly in underrepresented regions.

Given the rapid evolution of generative AI, it is reasonable to expect that the quality and thus geocoding capabilities of VLMs will continue to improve considerably in the future. Therefore, it is conceivable that the methodology presented here could be used to provide more accurate spatial information for disaster management. This would be particularly valuable in the context of social media analysis, where many posts and thus images lack precise georeferences. Consequently, the number of social media posts that can be georeferenced could increase substantially, enhancing the informative value and reliability of geo-social media-based analyses in disaster contexts. Moreover, the ability of VLMs to derive specific semantic content directly from images holds significant potential for filtering relevant information for such applications.

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Declarations

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, S.S., upon reasonable request.

No potential competing interest was reported by the author(s).

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Appendix

Figure 1: Distribution of Flickr images.

Figure 2: Quality of BLIP-2 geocoding results. The colours signify the quality of the [LLM](#) geocoding.

Distance to original location
 • <10km • 10-50km • 50-100km • 100-500km • >500km

Figure 3: Quality of LLaVA1.6 geocoding results. The colours signify the quality of the LLM geocoding.

Figure 4: Comparison of logarithmised distances between GPT-4o and human annotator results. The marginal plots show histograms for the distribution of the respective variable.

Figure 5: Local Moran's I for OpenFlamingo based on inverse distance spatial weights.